

УДК 37.01:378 (477)

АНАЛІЗ МЕТОДІВ ТРИВИМІРНОГО МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ У BLENDER ТА AUTODESK 3DS MAX

I.В. Вернер¹, О.М. Твердохліб², А.А. Лукін³

^{1,2}старший викладач кафедри конструювання, технічної естетики і дизайну, e-mail: ill3@ukr.net

³студент групи 132-23-3, e-mail: Lukin.A.A@nmu.one

^{1,2,3}Національний технічний університет «Дніпровська політехніка», Дніпро, Україна

Анотація. У роботі наводяться розглядаються методи тривимірного моделювання у найбільш популярних та розповсюджених середовищах моделювання. Аналізуються можливості методів та їх застосування для потреб конструювання та дизайну. Проводиться порівняння можливостей програмних середовищ, та надаються рекомендації щодо застосування.

Ключові слова: 3D моделювання, методи моделювання, конструювання, дизайн, можливості програмного продукту.

3D MODELING METHODS ANALYSIS IN BLENDER AND AUTODESK 3DS MAX

Ilya Verner¹, Olexander Tverdokhlib², Anton Lukin³

^{1,2}Lecturer, Department of Engineering and Generative Design, e-mail: ill3@ukr.net

³Student, e-mail: Lukin.A.A@nmu.one

^{1,2,3}Dnipro University of Technology, Dnipro, Ukraine

Abstract. This article delves into the exploration of 3D modeling methods employed in widely used and popular modeling environments. It analyzes the capabilities of these methods and their applications in the realm of engineering and design. A comparative analysis of the software environments' capabilities is conducted, and recommendations for their application are provided.

Keywords: 3D modeling, modeling methods, engineering, design, software environments.

Introduction. The world of 3D modeling, where virtual objects come to life on screens, captivates with its realism and limitless possibilities. However, behind this magic lies a complex process that combines technical skills, creativity, and the indispensable role of the human factor.

In today's world, 3D modeling plays a key role in the process of designing and constructing a wide variety of objects, from engineering parts to graphic compositions [1 - 3]. While technological progress is constantly evolving, there

is a certain limitation in the ability of artificial intelligence to replace human creativity and intuition.

In the modern design and engineering industry, many tasks related to 3D modeling are already automated using software tools and artificial intelligence algorithms. For example, there are programs that can generate basic forms based on specified parameters or by learning from samples. However, when creating complex designs or working on detailing and correcting minor flaws, the human factor is still an indispensable component. This is most often because it requires a sense of aesthetics and emotional perception.

Modeling methods are among the most important skills for a modern designer and engineer. They allow for the creation of complex and realistic models of objects in a virtual environment, which opens up a multitude of possibilities for developing innovative products, solving complex engineering tasks, and embodying creative ideas.

One of the first steps in developing any product is creating a prototype or concept. Thanks to modeling methods, the designer can quickly create a virtual model of their idea, identify its strengths and weaknesses, and experiment with different options.

Once the model is created, it can be subjected to thorough analysis and optimization. Modeling methods allow for various tests to be conducted, problems to be identified, and changes to be made before the physical prototype is even manufactured.

One of the most valuable capabilities of modeling methods is the ability to perform virtual testing and simulation. This allows engineers and designers to identify potential problems and refine the design even before the product is manufactured.

The purpose of this work is to analyze modeling methods, identify their areas of application, and compare the capabilities of the most powerful graphic editors Blender and 3Ds Max.

Methodology and Materials. In the field of design, multimedia, and visual effects, Autodesk 3Ds Max has been the leading software product for many years. For many decades, environment elements for feature films have been developed in this editor, visual effects for cinematography have been developed, and visualizations of a wide range of directions have been made. This software product can be called the standard of the 3D graphics industry. When inviting 3D designers to projects, employers highlight knowledge of this particular software product as a basic skill. The developers of the software environment annually update and expand its capabilities, monitor the needs of specialists, and maintain an open dialogue with the community. It should be recalled that for training

purposes Autodesk issues educational licenses for use with unlimited functionality. But for commercial use, the price of this software product is quite significant.

On the other hand, the Blender software product is completely free and distributed with open source code. Thanks to the funding of the development by world-famous industry giants, this editor is a powerful and high-quality system in which projects of a wide profile can be made. One of the features that contributes to the popularity of the project is the localization of the interface into many languages, including Ukrainian.

Both software products are equipped with tools for classic types of 3D modeling, and have their own view of this toolset. They also have their own modeling methods that are unique to them. Let's consider these methods in more detail.

Autodesk 3Ds Max provides the ability to use the following methods during modeling: object modeling, mesh, patch, polygonal, spline, surface, NURBS, loft (by sections), programming on maxscript, variations with various modifiers [4, 5].

Blender is also not far behind and allows modeling using the following methods: object modeling, polygonal, using curves (spline), artistic modeling (sculpting), by sections (loft), visual programming with geometric nodes, programming in the python language, variations with various modifiers [6, 7].

Let's consider the modeling methods in more detail.

The first we will look at is the object modeling method (Fig. 1). It consists in creating models from geometric primitives, that is, from objects that are contained in the libraries of the software environment itself. We can only choose them from a specific list, change their parameters (dimensions) and location in the scene (3D document). Most geometric primitives are the same in different graphics packages, that is, a cube, a sphere, a cylinder, and so on. So, this method can be used in any modeling environment.

Fig.1. – Examples of object modeling

In 3Ds Max, the mesh modeling method was the base during the creation of this software product many decades ago. It consists in the fact that the surface

of a 3D object is divided into triangles. It is possible to edit by switching to different modes, such as editing vertices, edges, faces and elements (Fig. 2, a). After some time, it became clear that there were not enough possibilities, and a new method was introduced - polygonal, which significantly expanded the editing capabilities. But the mesh method is still present, despite the fact that it is not developing. Thanks to this, it is possible to open and edit models that were created many years ago.

Fig.2. – Modeling examples: a – mesh modeling, b – polygonal modeling

The polygonal modeling method in 3Ds Max is the basic modeling method, and it is the one that is being promoted and developed. Modern modeling commands are added to the environment's command bar. During modeling, you can work in the following modes: editing vertices, edges, faces, holes (borders), elements (Fig. 2, b). It is in the polygonal modeling method that the soft selection tool (dependent distortions), deformation painting, and free-form modeling are implemented (Fig. 3).

Polygonal modeling in Blender is similar, the only difference is that there are 3 editing modes: editing vertices, edges, and faces. The possibilities are very similar and the working principles are almost identical.

The patch modeling method in 3Ds Max appeared because it was easier to develop a new tool than to rework the mesh modeling tools. It was promising for the development of curved surfaces, i.e. for the needs of organic modeling. But in the future, its developers also stopped developing it, but like the mesh method, they left it in the basic toolset of the graphics package. The method involves working in the following modes: editing vertices, edges, patches, elements, curvature levers (handles) (Fig. 4).

Fig.3. – Polygonal editing tools in 3DS Max: a – soft selection mode; b – paint deformation mode

Fig.4. – Patch modeling tools in 3DS Max

One of the widespread methods is the spline modeling method, which is based on the use of flat shapes, or contours, which consist of curves or straight segments. The library of standard splines includes such figures as: circle, arc, ellipse, rectangle, polygon and others. In 3Ds Max, the line tool works on the basis of the Bézier curve. That is, with a line you can make both straight and curved segments. The spline contour can be both closed and open. Depending on this, you can get a different result by applying the extrusion command to get a 3D object from a flat contour (Fig. 5, a). Also, the spline itself is not output for visualization, i.e. it is an auxiliary object, if you do not give it a 3D profile. You can also get 3D objects by creating a body of revolution based on a flat contour (Fig. 5, b).

In Blender, curves have three types: polygonal curve, Bézier curve, and NURBS curve. The forms of curves that can be added must be taken from an additional plugin, which is supplied by default with the environment, but it is in an inactive state.

Surface modeling can be considered a special case of spline modeling. It consists in creating 3D bodies using flat sections, which are connected by a frame consisting of lines. To obtain a 3D object, it is first necessary to develop the profiles of the future sections. Combine all profiles into a single spline. Use the crossection command to sequentially combine all sections to create a frame. A

surface modifier is applied to the frame, which results in a 3D figure (Fig. 6). After that, it is still possible to edit the curves to adjust the shape of the object, but if the frame is opened, the 3D part of the figure will disappear at the opening point.

Fig.5. – Spline examples: a – extruded splines; b – revolved splines

Fig.6. – Steps of creation model by surface modeling

The most well-known and widespread method of modeling by flat sections is the use of the loft modeling method. It is also a special case of spline modeling. To create a 3D model, it is necessary to create a trajectory (curve or straight line) along which to place different profile shapes (Fig. 7). This method has been used for many years in CAD systems and is supported by many 3D graphics editors. Objects obtained by this method can have a very complex organic surface shape.

The NURBS modeling method was founded in the 1950s by French designers who developed cars. It is based on modeling surfaces, each point of which depends on each other. In this way, it was possible to predict the behavior of, for example, a car body under load. In 3Ds Max, it is a whole modeling system in which it is possible for individual points to exist in a vacuum, or curves, even 3D surfaces in a single object (Fig. 8). To work with such objects, there is a whole set of tools that work only with Nurbs objects. Unfortunately, the developers have not updated this toolset for many years, and it has subsequently received some errors when used. However, it is also a standard tool in CAD systems.

In Blender, NURBS is focused on creating flat curvilinear figures, which are more often used for extrusion or creating bodies of revolution. But in Blender, curves are more often converted into a mesh model, which is then rotated, thus losing the ability to edit the shape of the 3D object with curves.

Fig.7. – Example of Loft modeling

Fig.8. – NURBS modeling

To create plants, animals, and other organic surfaces in 3Ds Max, there is a free transform tool located on the ribbon. It has several curvature brushes and retopology tools. In Blender, there is an environment for working with the sculpting modeling method. More often, there are separate plugins for working with this method, but in this case, the technology was successfully implemented and added to the 3D graphics package.

The principles of sculpting modeling are that a 3D blank (object) is created. Then it is finished with curvature brushes. Each of the brushes has its own functionality for creating curvatures, for example, there are extrusion brushes, bending, scratching, surface leveling, and many others (Fig. 9). It takes a lot of time and a lot of brush strokes to create the desired shape, so it is often necessary to have a graphics tablet for the convenience of using this method.

To get a more concise and visual representation of the software environments, let's create a comparison table of the capabilities of the graphics packages (Table 1).

Fig.9. – Examples of sculpting in Blender

Table 1. – Comparison of Blender and Autodesk 3ds Max

Feature	Blender	Autodesk3ds Max
Cost	Free and open-source	Commercial
Platform	Windows, macOS, Linux	Windows
User Interface	Intuitive and user-friendly	Complex and feature-rich
Modeling Methods	Wide range of methods, including object, polygonal, spline (curves), sculpting, and procedural modeling	Wide range of methods, including object, mesh, polygonal, patch, spline, surface, free form, and procedural modeling
Strengths	Free, open-source, large user community, intuitive interface, vast array of plugins	Powerful toolset, industry-standard features, well-suited for complex models
Weaknesses	Some features may require plugins, not as well-suited for professional use	Steep learning curve, expensive
Plugins & Add-ons	Vast library of free and paid plugins for extending functionality	Extensive library of commercial plugins for specialized workflows
Target Audience	Beginners, hobbyists, independent artists	Professionals, studios

Conclusions. Ultimately, the selection between Blender and 3ds Max hinges on the individual's specific objectives, experience level, and career aspirations. For those seeking an accessible and cost-effective platform to lay the foundation

of their 3D modeling skills, Blender emerges as an ideal companion. For seasoned professionals demanding unparalleled power, industry-standard capabilities, and the ability to tackle the most demanding projects, Autodesk 3ds Max stands as the undisputed champion.

This comprehensive analysis equips aspiring 3D modelers with the knowledge and insights necessary to make an informed decision that aligns with their unique needs and paves the way for a successful and fulfilling career in the ever-evolving realm of 3D modeling.

REFERENCES

1. Amani, Naghmeh & Yuly, A. (2019). 3D modeling and animating of characters in educational game. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 1193. 012025. 10.1088/1742-6596/1193/1/012025.
2. Silva, Pablo & Ruas, Vitor & Oliveira, Gustavo & Martinelli, Tiago & Machado de Oliveira, Antonio Victor & Schmidt, Marcelo & Andreão, Rodrigo & Mestria, Mário. (2018). Workflow to Optimization of 3D Models for Game Development. 225-229. 10.1109/SVR.2018.00041.
3. Forquesato, Luís & Borin, Juliana. (2018). Kids Block Coding Game: A game to introduce programming to kids. 10.5753/wei.2018.3502.
4. Abbasov, Iftikhar. (2017). Fundamentals of 3D modeling in the graphics system 3ds Max: Training Manual. 141p.
5. Stojanov, Igor & Ristevski, Blagoj & Kotevski, Zoran & Savoska, S.. (2016). Application of 3ds Max for 3D Modelling and Rendering. 133-144. 10.20544/AIT2016.17.
6. Hosen, Md Saikat & Ahmmed, Shahed & Dekkati, Sreekanth. (2019). Mastering 3D Modeling in Blender: From Novice to Pro. *ABC Research Alert*. 7. 169–180. 10.18034/ra.v7i3.654.
7. Dovramadjiev, Tihomir. (2015). Modern accessible application of the system Blender in 3D design practice. Publishing House "Union of Scientists - Stara Zagora". 10 – 13.

УДК 625.7/.8, 625.745.1/.2

ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ ПРОГРАМНИХ КОМПЛЕКСІВ ПІД ЧАС ПРОЄКТУВАННЯ ДОРОЖНІХ ВОДОПРОПУСКНИХ СПОРУД

М.В. Гаркуша¹

¹доцент кафедри мостів, тунелів та гідротехнічних споруд, e-mail: mykola.harkusha@ntu.edu.ua

¹Національний транспортний університет, Київ, Україна

Анотація. У роботі розглядаються підходи з проектування дорожніх водопропускних споруд з металевих гофрованих конструкцій із застосуванням програмних комплексів. Застосування комп'ютерних програм є засобом, за допомогою якого проєктувальник може приблизно визначити, яка конструкція водопропускної споруди є життєздатною в